

ORISON

innOvative **R**esearch Infrastructure based
on **S**tratospheric ballo**ON**s

DISEMINATION PLAN REPORT

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Deliverable

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1 DISSEMINATION PLAN INTRODUCTION

Dissemination activities were considered very important right from the beginning of the ORISON project and were clearly established as such in the grant agreement. A specific work package on dissemination was conceived to ensure proper actions in this regard.

The goal of the dissemination activities was to spread the ORISON concept and the results obtained during the project to the broadest audience possible including not only the scientific community, but also industry and general public. The dissemination objectives were conceived to promote the ORISON action and its applications to the market, while informing other potential procurers, solution developers, and general public about the project, the technology and the benefits of ORISON's platform to society.

The ORISON consortium recognized the importance of a good visual identity of the project brand. This "branding" was developed in the first month of the project, when the team worked on logos, colors, templates, website and related aspects. The idea of this branding work was to lead to a clear visibility profile, recognizable by the different commercial and public stakeholders and target audiences.

The ORISON consortium payed special attention to involve the target groups from the start of the project. The targeted groups included all stakeholders that were deemed relevant to the project by all consortium partners. Most important criteria to select this target audience was the relevance to the project. These criteria included synergies, commercial benefits, public outreach goals and European cooperation, as required in Horizon 2020 by the EC. These stakeholders were defined in more detail at the start of the project, and included the following

- Potential ORISON procurers (researchers that should need the infrastructure and make a good use of it)
- Potential ORISON end customers (public/private users of data acquired and processed thanks to the scientific instrumentation).
- Developers, Technology partners and other Researchers.
- The general public, EU citizens.
- Universities, to involve students in aspects of the project.
- Social media influencers.
- (Science) press and online media, like bloggers.
- Consortium partners' networks.
- Relevant industry associations.
- Other National and international projects / networks.
- Conference organizers and conference audiences.
- Other Horizon 2020 and FP7 related projects.
- Policy makers.

Even though the main research area was focused on Astronomy, the idea was to search for other potential science cases that could be done with the infrastructure on other areas of knowledge. The dissemination plan was made with a particular goal to reach potential

partners to join efforts for future stages of the project. With that goal, most of the effort of dissemination was made at the beginning of the project to collect feedback about the science cases and the potential uses of the gondola in order to define technical specifications.

In the following sections, the different activities that have been carried out with the main dissemination tools that we had foreseen are reported.

2 RESULTS

2.1 DISSEMINATION TOOLS

2.1.1 Brochures

Soon after creating logos a website and the main branding elements of the project, were made. Brochures in english were designed and printed. The brochures depicted in the figure below were created with the goal of handing them in the big conferences and in important events. 300 high-quality brochures were printed, with the goal of spreading 100 brochures in the three main conferences that happened in the summer of 2016 and were in our initial plans. The COSPAR conference is the main space research an engineering conference worldwide, usually with more than 1000 attendees. Then, the IMC-Meteoroids conference is the main conference about meteor research, with more than 300 attendees on the IMC part, and 150 the Meteoroids part. Then, the Scientific meeting of the Spanish Astronomical Society (SEA), is the biggest conference in astronomy in Spain, with more than 500 attendees.

Unfortunately, the brochures arrived too late for the first big conference (IMC-Meteoroids) and the COSPAR (COMmittee on SPace Reserch) conference was canceled due to the political-military instabilities in Turkey, where the meeting was going to take place.

The other big conference was the Scientific meeting of the Spanish Astronomical Society (SEA), which was a big success. Around 100 brochures were given to the attendees. The rest of the brochures were offered to the different partners.

Other big astronomical conferences like IAU general assembly are not be organized within the time frame of the project, and the European Week of Astronomy and Space Science (EWASS meeting) was already closed for contributions at the time of the start of the project. Also, brochures have been distributed by the Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía and through its own astronomical observatory to visitors of the facilities.

In a visit to the facilities of "Observatori de l'Ebre " and meeting with the Director Dr. David Altadill to explain the Project objectives, the observatory agreed to disseminate the project leaflet to the scientific visitors they could have. The Observatori de l'Ebre (OE) is a Research Institute founded by the Society of Jesus in 1904 to study Sun-Earth relationships. Over the years it has excelled in the study of earth currents, atmospheric electricity, seismology, solar and geomagnetic activity, and the terrestrial Ionosphere, and continues to do so today in the latter two fields. The fact of being constantly up-to-date regarding those scientific disciplines has led to unique innovations on a world-wide scale, and also resulted in the pioneering introduction of different geophysical techniques and studies in Spain. In addition to this aspect, the continuity and reliability of its

observations, with more than a hundred years of history, mean its magnetic, ionospheric, seismic, meteorological and solar records have an incalculable scientific value. As examples, it can be pointed out that the observatory's seismic and ionospheric records are the most extensive of their kind in Spain, and that the meteorological records go all the way back to 1880.

The OE is governed by a Non Profit Foundation. At present it forms part of the Ramon Llull University (URL) as a University Institute and it is also linked to the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) through a Collaboration Agreement. Within this Agreement, the OE is a Coordinated Centre of the CSIC. It has been associated or co-ordinated with this Council since its founding. It has also maintained a close collaboration with the National Institute of Meteorology (INM) ever since 1920 (now known as Agencia Estatal de Meteorología, AEMET), and subsequently with other Agencies such as the National Institute of Aero-spatial Technique (INTA), and the Cartographic Institute of Catalonia (ICC).

The Board of Trustees that governs the Foundation is composed of eleven Institutions: the National Geographic Institute (IGN), and three Departments of the Catalan Government - namely the Dept. of Environment; the Dept. of Innovation, Universities and Enterprise; and the Dept. of Territorial Policy and Public Works. Completing the Board's composition are the County Council of Tarragona, Town Council of Roquetes, Town Council of Tortosa, the already mentioned CSIC, AEMET, URL, and the Society of Jesus.

EY distributed around 20 other Project Brochures to clients. EY has distributed many other Brochures in EY Offices and EY events. EY organizes EY World Entrepreneur Of The Year™; Encuentro Alumni de EY

Stratospheric Observations

The goal of this European Horizon-funded project is to carry out feasibility and design studies of an astronomically oriented balloon facility that could deploy one or several small to medium-sized stabilized telescopes and a suite of other scientific instruments at light payloads to do state-of-the-art research at acceptable costs, and not necessarily from remote locations. The facility could also have other uses outside astronomy.

Some advantages of stratospheric observations in astronomy:

- Diffraction limited performance in imaging.
- High photometric precision.
- No clouds blocking the view.
- Access to Ultraviolet and Infrared wavelength ranges.
- Low sky brightness and no light pollution.
- Little or no Moon contribution to sky brightness.
- Interplanetary dust collecting.
- Optimize observation geometry (primary sciences and bright targets).
- More flexibility than observing from space platforms.
- Cheaper than space missions.
- Fast development compared to land or sea-based.
- Synergies with other facilities and ground-based.

Institutions & Participants

Would you like to observe from the high Stratosphere? Join us at <http://orison.iaa.es/content/future-partners> Or contact us at info@orison.eu

Your feedback will help us to design and advocate a low-cost, balloon-based research platform within the innovative Research Infrastructure based on Stratospheric Balloons (ORISON) project. The project is currently undertaken by the Instituto de Astronomía de Andalucía (IAA-CSIC), the University of Stuttgart, UCL & York, and the Max Planck Institute for Extraterrestrial Physics with the goal to secure the feasibility and identify potential funding schemes to create the infrastructure.

The envisioned balloon-based platform would offer observation conditions similar to that of a space mission, such as demonstrated by highly successful missions in the past but at considerably lower costs.

The total concept uses:

- Flight altitude ca. 35 km.
- Duration between several hours and up to one day possible.
- One or several telescopes of $\sim 0.5\text{ m}$ diameter.
- Several instruments and payloads possible per payload.
- Autonomy: low weight instruments for complementary science.
- Autonomous recovery system of operation with regular calls for proposal.

To design the detailed payload and final infrastructure we are seeking input from different teams that can have different science cases and can be interested in the final infrastructure. So please visit our webpage to provide your input and fill the feedback form in any terms as needed for different science cases.

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Project

ORISON is a project aimed at building several fields of astronomy with the requirement of scientific instrumentation. The current actions addressed focus on feasibility and design studies of an astronomically oriented research infrastructure based on a balloon facility. The infrastructure can deploy one or several small to medium-sized telescopes and a suite of other scientific instruments at light payloads to do state-of-the-art research at acceptable costs, and not necessarily from remote locations.

THE NEED

Astronomical observations (and astronomical experiments on Earth and elsewhere) affected by the Earth's atmosphere. There are many problems associated with observations from Earth's atmosphere. To name a few, atmospheric turbulence distorts the image quality that telescopes can detect; atmospheric absorption completely blocks the radiation of certain wavelengths; the scattering and emission by the atmosphere cause enormous background noise; and bad weather prevents observations. The major limitations are in observations spread and through the use of telescopes of different parts of the electromagnetic spectrum, including the ultraviolet.

Key observations used to do state-of-the-art astronomical observations (astronomy) to understand some of the most important particles and we can measure parameters in the universe. Information from these data can give a glimpse of valuable information on astrophysical processes. We also try to observe and study particles and bodies that orbit within the Earth, as they are important information on our closest astrophysical environment. Most of the astronomical results refer to this second group of objects as "spaceborne" rather than observations, but they are actually observations, because they cannot support the experiment and we are the measurement.

APPROACH

Our approach is the use of small low-cost stratospheric balloons, also called hobby or piggy-back balloons, equipped with high-resolution astronomical instruments and other instruments that can be used to study their physical emission. They can carry a few kg of payload for a few days. "Spaceborne" tools, and should be developed and tested in a laboratory or in an astronomical suitable astronomical environment. These balloons-based instruments should be designed to be launched from remote areas on Earth, and preferably from remote areas not in habitable areas near the Earth's Pole and Antarctica.

Scientific Cases

The solution proposed in ORISON is more flexible, more specific, and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences.

Stellar occultation studies: Many occultation studies have been carried out. Also, occultation studies have been carried out in the past. However, the current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences. The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences. The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences.

Study of other time-critical astronomical events: For instance, the observation of a transient event with a very short duration and very faint light can be missed if the observation is not planned in advance. However, the current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences. The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences.

Studies of serendipitous stellar occultations: The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences. The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences.

High spatial resolution imaging and study of the planets at all epochs, near real-time: The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences. The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences.

Detection of deep ground water systems: The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences. The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences.

Staking equipment, particularly in high altitudes: The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences. The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences.

Study of disks around stars and exoplanet formation: The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences. The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences.

Collecting interstellar dust particles: The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences. The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences.

Complementing ALMA observations: The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences. The current approach is more flexible and of lower cost, than previous balloon experiences.

Fig. 1. Brochure of ORISON which was distributed at conferences and other events

2.1.2 Business cards

Personal business cards were printed with the names of the people more involved in the dissemination activities and the people with key roles in ORISON. They were used in all the scientific meetings and other meetings.

Fig. 2. Example of business card of one of us

2.1.3 Web page

The project website (www.orison.eu) was one of the first deliverables of this project and was put together as soon as logos and other branding elements were done in collaboration with designers, after the kickoff meeting of ORISON, when the logos were selected from a different set of possibilities. The website description has its own specific document so it is not described at length here. It has basically three parts, one for the general description of the project (for the general public and for scientists), a private part and an interactive part (which is interactive with the twitter account) and also has a regular link to the facebook, youtube and twitter accounts.

The webpage has been one of the key references for documentation and to provide more information to the potential partners and interested people, including the general public. Although the webpage itself was difficult to update because of difficulties with the design company that built the page (not with the hosting, which was at IAA-CSIC servers), the twitter feed automatically updated the web. A correct analysis of the web statistics is nearly impossible because the company that built the page did not configure it properly until November 2016 for such a purpose, but at that time most of the dissemination activities that took advantage of the website had been carried out according to the project plans. Also, part of the traffic is spam bots, especially the Trump election spam bots.

Fig. 3 Statistics of the website since november 2016.

One of the most useful part of the website was the web form to collect feedback directly from the potential partners. The results that can be made public are on the ANNEX.

2.1.4 Social media

As a proactive dissemination tool, the different social media networks have been used with success. For example, the twitter account got 7.2k visits, which is a significant number. Facebook does not provide long term statistics, but the most viewed post had 2.3 k views. The most active tweet was related with the presentations at the conference of the Spanish Astronomical Society.

The most viewed post on facebook was related with the Orison Pathfinder video of the Perseids meteor shower in August 2016. Also, some of the members have used their personal accounts to spread the project, and for example, the tweet of ASM of the December 14th had 18.000 impressions, 117 retweets and 158 likes.

Fig. 4 Example of a high impact tweet regarding one of the ORISON pahtfinder test missions.

Fig. 5 Statistics of the ORISON twitter account.

Fig. 6 Statistics of the youtube ORISON account

Fig. 7 Statistics of the last month of the Facebook account and the most important posts of the last year.

In youtube we uploaded several videos of different phases of the outreach and pathfinder ORISON missions. The youtube channel can be reached at:

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC9Pt1-e2v45OzCFficYMuGw>

The visits to the different videos make a total of 2749 as of 28 July 2017. There are other videos that were not uploaded directly to this channel of youtube. Besides, the ORISON project was featured in other youtube videos of colleagues.

2.1.5 Roll Ups

Four roll ups were made and like the brochures, they were planned to be used in the main conferences, exhibitions and outreach activities. As they were big, they only could be used in the scientific meeting of the Spanish Astronomical Society, they were reused as promotional element at the Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía hall, where they are permanently exposed (whenever they are not in conferences and activities such as the European science week and other outreach events). They were written both in english and spanish.

Fig. 8 Rollups in spanish and english of the ORISON project for events and conferences. In this picture they are shown at the IAA-CSIC hall, where they are permanently exhibited except when they are moved to conferences or events.

2.1.6 Articles and press releases

Three articles were written for general outreach magazines. One was written for the Complutense University of Madrid^a, as ORISON is partially a follow-up of some pioneer research done at that university on the PRO-AM (professional-amateur) collaboration in the field of astronomy.

Also a press release was issued at the Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía (<http://old.iaa.es/content/project-orison-study-cosmos-stratospheric-balloons-launched>) and an article in its outreach magazine was written. This outreach magazine, which is

^a http://www.ucm.es/data/cont/docs/3-2017-02-15-2017_02_not7.pdf

both in printed and in web formats^b has typically 2000 prints plus downloads and is published every three weeks.

Also an article about the project appeared in the EU journal horizon-magazine.eu^c.

2.1.7 Data management: Zenodo

Following some EU recommendations and guidelines, a large part of the material in form of documents that can be released (public documents), such as presentations, outreach videos, public deliverables and RAW data, have been posted on the EU recommended repository: ZENODO^d. To have an organized database, a community has been created at that portal.

For instance, thanks to this policy of open data, the RAW data of the ORISON Pathfinder 3/Daedalus XXI mission[1][2] was used by Francisco Ocaña[3] for his thesis. Part of that work has been presented in the public document feasibility report.

2.2 CONFERENCES AND TALKS AT UNIVERSITIES AND RESEARCH CENTERS:

With the goal of getting direct feedback from the potential users, a number of talks were given all around Europe trying to optimize the travel costs.

2.2.1 IAA Seminar Granada - (Talk + On-line)

2016-02-04	Granada, Spain and Internet, Approx. ~ 30 present and 153 online (26/7/2017). Performed by J. L. Ortiz. Broadcasted talk about ORISON, mainly focused on astronomy for the astronomers and atmospheric scientist of the Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía. IAA seminars are scientific and technical talks given every week with the goal of fostering the scientific and technical exchange at IAA-CSIC and in Spain. Talks are given by IAA-CSIC scientists or by visiting scientists. http://www.iaa.es/en/seminars
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^b <http://revista.iaa.es/content/arranca-el-proyecto-orison-para-el-estudio-del-cosmos-desde-globos-estratosf%C3%A9ricos>

^c https://horizon-magazine.eu/article/helium-balloons-offer-low-cost-flights-stratosphere_en.html#.WUqQ_CoMq_s.twitter

^d <https://zenodo.org/communities/orison>

	<p>http://www.iaa.es/seminars/orison-proyecto-instrumentacion-astronomica-estratosferica</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a7KiOXQt-Ig</p> <p>The project was received with interest by many researches in different fields although most researchers are already involved in other instrumental projects so only a few potential partners were identified. Particular strong interest was manifested by teams working on Transient Luminous Events in the terrestrial atmosphere and also from the extrasolar planet science community.</p>
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2.2.2 RIA Space -Tec Madrid (Conference)

<p>2016-02-10 2016-02-12</p>	<p>Madrid, Spain, Approx. ~ 100. Performed by J.J. Moreno.</p> <p>The RIA is a network for astronomy infrastructures in Spain, which, among other things, organizes conferences on instrumentation and facilities, present or future http://riastronomia.es/en/. This particular event was aimed at the Space Community in Spain. It is the biggest conference on astronomical instrumentation in Spain.</p> <p>The specific program of the conference can be obtained in the specific page of this particular RIA-series conference^e</p> <p>Presented [12]: López-Moreno, J. J., Ortiz, J. L., Duffard, R., Wolf, J., Schindler, K., Müller, T., ... Baztarrica, J. (2016, May).</p>
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^e<https://spacetec.cab.inta-csic.es/svoMeetings/index.php?mid=23&action=page&pagename=Workshop2016/Program>

	<p>ORISON un proyecto de instrumentación astronómica estratosférica. Zenodo. http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.53051</p> <p>The project was received with interest by many researchers and technicians in different fields, although most researchers are already involved in other instrumental projects, mainly space-based so only a few potential partners were identified.</p>
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2.2.3 DEIMOS IMAGING (Stakeholders)

2016-02-16	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON project and possible future collaboration as sponsors.
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2.2.4 Lucky Star

<p>2016-4-20</p> <p>2016-4-22</p>	<p>Observatoire de Paris-Meudon. Kick-off meeting of EU H2020 project “Lucky Star”. The “Lucky Star” project deals with topics of stellar occultations and the ORISON platform can have an impact on improving the observation of stellar occultations, hence it was considered that it was relevant if ORISON could be presented there taking advantage of the visit of our close collaborator P. Santos-Sanz who is well acquainted with the project. Talk given by P. Santos (IAA-CSIC). Estimated attendance ~20 people.</p> <p>http://beyond-neptune.lesia.obspm.fr/sites/beyond-neptune/IMG/pdf/Orison_santos.pdf</p> <p>Interest was perceived from the participants and from the principal investigator, but the general project was viewed as something somewhat futuristic</p>
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2.2.5 SPRI (Stakeholders)

2016-05-09	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON project. Bilbao (Spain)
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2.2.6 AIP (Talk)

2016-05-17	<p>Potsdam, Germany. AIP is an important astrophysical institution in Europe, One of the oldest observatories of the world http://www.aip.de/en Approx. people that attended the talk ~15.</p>
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	<p>Audience mainly astronomers. It didn't get to all the members because it was announced with little time.</p> <p>As a side note, the project was received with a lot of skepticism but the audience was not familiarized with airborne observatories.</p> <p>Carried out by A. Sánchez de Miguel. https://twitter.com/Orison_EU/status/732531790771019776</p>
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2.2.7 FU-Berlin, Institute for Space Sciences (Talk)

<p>2016-05-17</p>	<p>Information on the Institute for Space Sciences can be obtained here: https://userpage.fu-berlin.de/geoiss/en/home.html</p> <p>The talk was performed by: A. Sánchez de Miguel.</p> <p>Approx. people ~ 10.</p> <p>Remote sensing community mainly. Among the main topics of research, study and teaching at the Institute of Space Sciences are problems of airborne and spaceborne remote sensing.</p> <p>Results: Some people said that could be interesting for their research. Some possible contacts with Google Loon stratospheric program [13].</p>
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2.2.8 ESTEC – ESA (Talk)

2016-06-02 2016-06-03	<p>Noordwijk, Netherlands (by P. Maier). ESTEC is the technical heart - the incubator of the European space effort - where most ESA projects are born and where they are guided through the various phases of development. Introduction of the ORISON concept to scientific and institutional representatives at ESA in Noordwijk, Netherlands (among others atmospheric scientists, exoplanet scientists, Ariel space mission team representatives).</p> <p>Results: Interesting contact on biology science and Sprites (and Aurora)</p> <p>Contact with other groups and other ways to spread the project.</p>
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2.2.9 International Meteor Conference 2016 (Conference)

2016-06-02 2016-06-05	<p>Egmond – the Netherlands, presentation performed by A. Sánchez de Miguel.</p> <p>This was a Pro-Am meeting about meteor detection, organized by the International Meteor Organization. Meteor science is one of the science topics for which a stratospheric platform can provide very valuable results and that is the main reason for approaching them. This is the biggest PRO-AM conference in meteor research. Every year. http://imc2016.amsmeteors.org/ Another PRO-AM stratospheric mission was presented [8].</p> <p>Few contacts. A poster was presented. More than 300 participants.</p>
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2.2.10 Meteoroids (Conference)

<p>2016-06-06</p>	<p>ESTEC, Noordwijk - the Netherlands, 6 June 2016, performed by A. Sánchez de Miguel and P. Maier. Biggest world conference about professional meteor research. Held very three years. Around 150 participants.</p> <p>https://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/meteoroids2016/</p> <p>A lot of interest on the project by several groups.</p> <p>We met people involved on the Cost action BigSkyEarth.</p> <p>Poster presented [7]: Sánchez de Miguel, A., Ortiz, J. Luis ., López-Moreno, J. J., Duffard, R., Maier, P., Mueller, T., ... Graf, F. (2016). ORISON, stratospheric instrumentation project with potential applications in meteoroid science. Zenodo. http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.55563</p>
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2.2.11 PCP/PPI (Discussion)

2016-06-07	Frankfurt, Germany, by P. Maier. Participation in the German working group on PCP/PPI activities under H2020, introduction of the ORISON project to the German PCP/PPI community. Approx. 20 participants.
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2.2.12 Leiden University (Talk)

2016-06-07	Leiden, the Netherlands, performed by A. Sánchez de Miguel. Talk in the Astronomy department. Results: Talk thanks a contact found by Facebook. Manly astronomers. Done because of the Meteoroids meeting. Approximate people ~ 10. Some people interested but no contact after the talk. Interest from the EU Universe Awareness International Project Manager for educational purposes.
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2.2.13 Nijmegen University (Talk)

<p>2016-06-08</p>	<p>Nijmegen , the Netherlands, performed by A. Sánchez de Miguel. Approx.: 15 people. Talk in the Astronomy department. Talk was given thanks to a Facebook contact, an example of how a social network helps on the dissemination in a more effective way than other internet resources. Audience: Mainly astronomers. Done because of the Meteoroids meeting nearby. Approximate people ~ 15. Some people interested but no contact after the talk.</p> <p>https://twitter.com/AstroRoque/status/740534573264732160</p>
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2.2.14 SPIE (Conference)

2016-06-26
2016-07-01

Edinburg – United Kingdom. Performed by F. Ocaña and A. Sánchez de Miguel. SPIE is a large conference, the major conference on technology in astronomy and related fields. This edition was focused on Astronomical infrastructures. Special session about ballooning was included. More than 1.000 attendees.

<http://spie.org/conferences-and-exhibitions/astronomical-telescopes-and-instrumentation>

There was a talk about the Daedalus probes + one or two slides about ORISON (it was impossible to introduce full talk because the abstract submission was closed before of the beginning of the project).

https://twitter.com/Orison_EU/status/748508632334106624

The paper "Ocaña, F., de Miguel, A. S., Conde, A., & Team, D. (2016). Low cost multi-purpose balloon-borne platform for wide-field imaging and video observation. arXiv preprint arXiv:1609.07952." was presented. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.59213>

2.2.15 SEA (Conference)

2016-07-19

Bilbao, Spain Performed by J.L. Ortiz, A. Sánchez de Miguel, R. Duffart, P. Santos and E. del Mar.

SEA is the biggest astronomical conference in Spain, with more than 500 attendees. It is bianual. The astrophysical community in Spain is very strong thanks in part to the powerful astronomical facilities that the country hosts. Info on the conference is at <http://www.sea-astronomia.es/drupal/SEA2016>

Apart from the talk presenting the project in the regular meeting sessions, a special session only for ORISON was organized with the presence of approx. 40 people. Because it could only be booked at lunch time a catering was organized, which was a good attractor and in the end several people of the audience contributed to filling out the online web form that we had in our website to collect input from the scientific community. The special session on ORISON was announced to the spanish astronomy community through the SEA e-mailing distribution list, which reaches more than 500 accounts.

Two talks were given about ORISON, one about ORISON pathfinder missions and meteor detection, and another one about the ORISON applications on research of solar system bodies.

https://twitter.com/Orison_EU/status/755374184763625472

<https://twitter.com/pmission/status/756043103904169985>

<https://twitter.com/mekonto/status/756045489754124288>

https://twitter.com/Orison_EU/status/755360735916658688

2.2.16 Junta de Andalucía (stakeholder/policy maker)

2016-07-28	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON project and possible future collaboration as sponsors or as customers or as facilitators. Hosted at IAA-CSIC.
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2.2.17 EY (internal talk)

2016-07-28	Presentation of the ORISON project and objectives internally for possible engagement with other clients of Ernst and Young / prospects and with ongoing projects. (Spain)
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2.2.18 COSPAR (Conference)

2016-08	Largest conference Worldwide about space engineering. Every two years. Usually more than 1.000 attendees. Abstract was submitted and plans had been made to make to have a good dissemination and feedback but it was cancelled because of military coup in Turkey.
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2.2.19 ASIME (Conference)

2016-09-21 2016-09-22	<p>Luxemburg. Talk given by P. Maier. Participation in the ASIME (Asteroid Science Intersections with In-Space Mine Engineering) conference 2016 in Luxembourg to present the potential of balloon-based telescopes to detect water and hydration tracers. Approx. 80 participants, mainly from science and industry. There was plenty of interest in the platform to do asteroid science. Info on the conference http://fmispace.fmi.fi/index.php?id=asime16</p>
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2.2.20 URTHECAST (Stakeholders)

2016-09-23	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON project and possible future collaboration as sponsors. Virtual meeting.
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2.2.21 zero2infinity (Stakeholders)

2016-11-02	Meeting with potential future industry partners (zero2infinity) in Barcelona, Spain. Meeting in person. Very useful to learn about new technologies in ballooning and operating them. All ORISON partners participated because it was held taking advantage of an internal mid-term ORISON internal meeting in Barcelona.
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2.2.22 World View Inc. (Stakeholders)

2016-11-03	Virtual group meeting with potential future industry partners (World View Inc.) Very useful meeting to learn about new technologies in balloon launch and operations.
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2.2.23 ERICSSON (Stakeholders)

2016-11-15	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON project and possible future collaboration as sponsors.
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2.2.24 Twinkle project (Stakeholders)

2016-11-22	Virtual group meeting with potential future stakeholders/partners (team of the Twinkle project, which is a space mission concept for exoplanet spectroscopy). Info on the project http://www.twinkle-spacemission.co.uk/
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2.2.25 INDITEX (Stakeholders)

2016-12-01	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON project and possible future collaboration as sponsors. Arteixo (Spain)
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2.2.26 Agrupación Astronómica de Madrid (Talk)

2017-01-12	<p>Madrid, by A. Sánchez de Miguel. Attendance, approx. ~70 people. Talk about the PRO-AM collaboration on the ORISON Pathfinder missions to test the case study of the meteor detection from the stratosphere. Amateur association which has its own program to launch small stratospheric balloons.</p> <p>https://twitter.com/Orison_EU/status/819556418768502787</p>
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2.2.27 Swedish Space Corporation (Stakeholders)

2017-02-08	Meeting with potential future industry partners (Swedish Space Corporation) in Kiruna, Sweden.
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2.2.28 fonYou (Stakeholders)

2017-02-14	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON project and possible future collaboration.
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2.2.29 German national ESA Technology days (Discussion)

2017-02-15	Participation in the German national ESA Technology days (dissemination of project activities among institutional and industrial actors) in Munich, Germany. Done by P. Maier.
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2.2.30 Telefonica (Stakeholders)

2017-02-15	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON project and possible future collaboration as sponsors. Madrid (Spain)
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2.2.31 EY (internal talk)

2017-02-28	Presentation of the ORISON project and objectives internally for possible engagement with other clients / prospects and with ongoing projects. (Spain)
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2.2.32 SPRI (Stakeholders)

2017-03-23	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON project. Bilbao (Spain)
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2.2.33 Airbus Defense (Stakeholders)

2017-04-07	Discussion on potential collaboration with Airbus Defense and Space in Taufkirchen, Germany. Given by P. Maier.
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2.2.34 VISUAL (Stakeholders)

2017-04-12	Virtual meeting with the CEO of VISUAL for the presentation & introduction of the ORISON project and possible future collaboration as sponsors/users.
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2.2.35 23rd ESA Symposium on European Rocket & Balloon Programmes (Conference)

2017-06-11 2017-06-15	Presentation of the ORISON concept at the 23 rd ESA Symposium on European Rocket & Balloon Programmes and Related Research to a scientific, institutional, and industrial audience in Visby, Sweden. http://pac.spaceflight.esa.int/ This is the largest and most specific conference on ballooning science and technology held in Europe. It was a key conference for many of the goals and interests of ORISON. Talk given by P. Maier.
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2.2.36 MPE CAS group (Talk)

2017-06-30	Presentation of the ORISON concept to a scientific audience in the Max Planck Institute for Extraterrestrial Physics MPE CAS group retreat at Schloss Ringberg, Germany. Given by P. Maier
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2.2.37 EL CORTE INGLES (Stakeholders)

2017-07-11	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON project and possible future collaboration as sponsors. Madrid (Spain)
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2.2.38 TU München (Discussion)

2017-07-12	Discussion on potential collaborations with the Academic Student Group Space of TU München in Garching, Germany. Given by P. Maier
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2.2.39 Space Up (Talk)

2017-07-23	Presentation of the ORISON concept at the SpaceUp Stuttgart popular science conference in Stuttgart, Germany. Approx. 100 participants.
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2.2.40 MPE, Garching (Talk)

2017-07-12 2017-07-25	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON concept to student interns at MPE, Garching, Germany. By P. Maier.
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2.2.41 Observatory de l'Ebre (Stakeholders)

2017-07-25	Presentation & introduction of the ORISON concept and conclusions achieved to student to the Observatory Director. The Observatory de l'Ebre will collaborate distributing ORISON Brochures to their visitors.
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2.2.42 SKANSENSE (Stakeholders)

2017-07-28	Presentation of the ORISON project and possible future collaboration. Madrid (Spain)
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2.2.43 European Planetary Science Congress 2017 (Conference)

2017-09-17 2017-09-22	Presentation of ORISON at the European Planetary Science Congress 2017 in Riga, Latvia. By P. Maier.
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2.3 CONFERENCE ATTENDANCE (PRESENCE TO MAKE CONTACTS):

2.3.1 First International ECSA Conference 2016

2016-05-11 2016-05-12	Berlin. By A. Sánchez de Miguel. First meeting of the European Citizen Science Association. More than 500 attendees. Various contacts were made related to teledetection and and astromy. Casual contact with a remote sensing Institute. Good second contact through e-mail.
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2.3.2 ESA Living Planet

2016-05-09 2016-05-13	Prague. By A. Sánchez de Miguel. Largest conference in Europe about remote sensing. Large conference with more than 3000 participants. Contacts were made with companies like VITO and other commercial operators such as Planet Labs and Deimos-imaging. No special interest in teledetection at night although Airbus and Eurosense are researching that market. http://lps16.esa.int/
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2.3.3 ALAN 4th International Conference- ALAN 2016

2016-09-26 2016-09-28	Cluj-Napoca-Romania. By A. Sánchez de Miguel. Largest conference about light pollution, held every two years. Lots of contributions about nocturnal remote sensing. More than 200 attendees. Contact with the Alder Planetarium ballooning program (http://farhorizonsproject.com/blog/)
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2.3.4 Cost-Action BigSkyEarth

We have found that there are some people interested in a similar concept and contacts have been made. This Cost action tries to connect astronomical community and earth observation communities that are using bigdata. They have a potential stratospheric mission too.

2.4 NEWSLETTER:

A newsletter was prepared and distributed to contacts reached by PM, JLO and ASM. Only one newsletter has been issued so far, and we will send a new one by the end of the project with the main results. On that contact list there are 84 interested contacts on ORISON. The first newsletter was sent on 18/07/2016.

2.5 PROBE LAUNCHES (ORISON PATHFINDER MISSIONS):

As an outreach, dissemination and research tool we have continued the PRO-AM collaboration between the IAA-CSIC and the Daedalus group [9], started by A. Sanchez de Miguel. In those launches we have tested interesting equipment like the high sensitivity Sony A7S camera and recovery devices that have been of great use for the Technical report and feasibility report. This type of launches draws in general a lot of media attention, but most of them do not have scientific relevance because most of them are carried out in daylight and there is little science that can be done in our field. However, nocturnal stratospheric balloon flights are very interesting for various scientific projects like those mentioned in ORISON such as meteor detection [5] [7] and nocturnal remote sensing [10]. With these launches we have put in practice some radical approaches that are mentioned in the feasibility report deliverable, such as the use of ultralight weight ultrasensitive cameras of new technology. The experience has been very important to know in practice limitations that were not known for consultants regarding regulation matters.

Each launch had a PR and some impact on the media.

During the development of the project, it has also been possible to get some extra resources for a small project inside the Stars4all European program [11]. Skyeye will consist of the development of an open hardware solution to make possible to obtain stratospheric nocturnal images of cities at low cost.

Also, the stratospheric flights done by amateurs get a lot of media attention, so with the goal of getting some resources, more experience and test one of the science cases (meteor detection from the stratosphere) it was decided to continue the PRO-AM collaboration

with the Daedalus group already started by one of the ORISON partners. Six missions were planned, although because of several problems only three have been carried out.

2.5.1 Lyrids 2016 (done)

We made a Press Release about the launch. It has appeared in some media (list of the clipping). Small impact but useful to have some own images. Launched from Talavera de la Reina, Toledo, Spain.

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fJvvInWPC9s&t=287s>

News clipping:

<http://www.europapress.es/ciencia/astronomia/noticia-arranca-proyecto-orison-estudiar-cosmos-globos-20160503191057.html>

<http://www.granadadigital.es/tag/instituto-de-astrofisica-de-andalucia/?print=print-search>

2.5.2 Perseids 2016 (done)

Mission launched from Almadén, Ciudad Real, Spain. Data pending of being analyzed. It had very big impact and good scientific results.

Source[6]: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aEYE7Gk_Z5U

News clips:

<http://old.iaa.es/es/content/la-lluvia-de-estrellas-de-las-perseidas-podr%C3%ADa-alcanzar-los-quinientos-meteoros-por-hora>

<http://www.20minutos.es/noticia/2810812/0/perseidas-lluvia-estrellas-intensa-agosto/>

<http://www.rtve.es/noticias/20160803/lluvia-estrellas-perseidas-espera-este-ano-hasta-500-meteoros-hora-5-veces-mas-ocasiones-anteriores/1380885.shtml>

<https://intereconomia.com/tendencias/ciencia-tendencias/la-lluvia-perseidas-sera-5-veces-mas-intensa-20160804-0826/>

<http://www.lavanguardia.com/vida/20160803/403662677131/lluvia-perseidas.html>

<http://www.planetaincognito.es/2016/08/06/este-fin-de-semana-se-juntan-dos-lluvias-de-estrellas-las-perseidas-y-las-delta-acuaridas/>

<http://www.heraldo.es/noticias/suplementos/tercer-milenio/divulgacion/2016/08/10/lagrimas-san-lorenzo-bajo-efecto-jupiter-1006425-2121028.html>

<http://www.diario4v.com/tendencias/ciencia/2016/8/8/perseidas-lluvia-estrellas-esta-semana-11177.html>

<https://es.noticias.yahoo.com/el-doble-perseidas-en-2016-claves-para-ver-134205808.html>

<http://www.diaridegirona.cat/fets-gent/2016/08/03/pluja-dels-perseids-sera-aquest/797321.html>

<http://www.navarrainformacion.es/2016/08/03/las-perseidas-podrian-alcanzar-este-ano-los-500-meteoros-hora/>

<http://www.objetivocastillalamancha.es/contenidos/region/llegan-perseidas-este-ano-pueden-alcanzar-quinientos-meteoros-hora>

<https://es.sott.net/article/47504-La-lluvia-de-meteoros-de-las-Perseidas-2016-sera-cinco-veces-mas-intensa-que-otros-anos>

<http://blog.nuestroclima.com/observar-la-lluvia-estrellas-las-perseidas/>

<http://www.eldigitaldeasturias.com/noticias/espana-mira-al-cielo-noche-de-perseidas/>

<http://www.apaa.org.pa/blog-y-noticias/entry/perseidas-con-500-meteoros-por-hora.html>

<http://www.lavanguardia.com/local/sevilla/20160811/403856990094/primeras-perseidas-hd-andalucia.html>

2.5.3 Sprites mission (September 2016)- Not done

This mission was planned with the goal of getting images of Sprites. Unfortunately, a change of the regulation in Spain for balloon launches makes mandatory that the flights are scheduled with more than 20 days. As the storms are not predictable with that long range of time, it was not a feasible mission.

2.5.4 Geminids 2016 (spectroscopy) - Partially done

Launched from Montijo, Extremadura, Spain. This mission was supposed to be ready to test spectroscopy mode, it but was not possible to get a diffraction grating in time with the required features, so the mission was carried out in the simple video mode. It has been analyzed by F. Ocaña [1]. One of the goals was to make double observations with meteor cameras of the Canary Islands (Miquel Serra et. al IAC) in order to be able to derive orbits. Unfortunately, the team at the Canary Islands was not able to detect faint meteors due to a high aerosol content in the atmosphere.

Source: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r_THqTpfU7s&t=1s

News clips:

<http://www.juntaex.es/comunicacion/noticia&idPub=20723#.WXlaqojiCo>

http://www.elconfidencial.com/tecnologia/2016-12-13/lluvia-geminidas-mejores-dias-noches-diciembre_1303053/

http://www.lainformacion.com/ciencia-y-tecnologia/ciencias-naturales/astronomia/Geminidas-actividad-estrellas-fugaces-diciembre_0_980602236.html

<http://diariodeavisos.espanol.com/2016/12/la-lluvia-las-geminidas-se-ofrecera-directo-desde-canarias/>

<http://www.mediavida.com/foro/ciencia/geminidas-2016-como-ver-lluvia-navidad-574610>

http://www.eldiario.es/tenerifeahora/sociedad/lluvia-Geminidas-directo-Canarias_0_590392106.html

<http://www.diariovasco.com/sociedad/ciencia/201612/17/caza-record-estelar-20161216201148-rc.html>

<http://tuotrodiario.hola.com/noticias/2016121264864/noches-13-14-mejores-ver-lluvia-geminidas/>

2.5.5 Occultation mission (January 2017) - Not executed.

This mission was planned to detect a stellar occultation. It was not possible to carry out the experiment because the complexity was much higher and there were not enough technical, human and economic resources to make all the necessary preparations and to finance all the instruments and the launch.

2.5.6 Scintillation and sky brightness test. - Scheduled.

This mission is Scheduled for any moment during 2017 by using the funding of the SkyEYE project.

2.6 TELEVISION APPEARANCES

Because of these press releases, the project had appeared on several Spanish television shows. Some of them were Perseids 2016 El Tiempo [Antena 3], Más vale tarde [La Sexta], Geminids 2016, Noticias, Canal Extremadura, Noticias [RTVE] and the internet broadcasting TV,[SKYLIVE.TV].

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s9Uqixu044g>

Based on the share of these television programs we estimate that the ORISON videos were seen by more than 2 million people^e

2.7 SIDEPRODUCTS OF ORISON: SCIENCE DONE BY ORISON ON ALTIMETRIC

There are other scientific documents that have been produced linked to the research connected directly or indirectly to ORISON that have generated some dissemination.

The article Sánchez de Miguel et. al. 2017[2] about the most common sensor to measure the sky brightness, the SQM, ended producing a large impact with 23 impacts on Altimetric^f and 3 citations. This was the sensor used during the Perseids mission: Orison 2/Daedalus XX.

There are another two articles related with the theoretical and practical use of DSLR cameras for remote sensing at night (one of the scientific cases of ORISON) that will be published soon.

One, has been presented in several conferences and has appeared already in some media: This is the work about the connection between breast cancer and light pollution.

Also, other research like the Francisco Ocaña thesis had some impact on:

^f <https://oxfordjournals.altmetric.com/details/18915692>

News clips:

<http://web3.eldia.es/palma/2017-04-21/3-Asocian-contaminacion-luminica-cancer-mama-prostata.htm>

3 OVERALL EVALUATION

In general, there is a lot of interest about the topic in all the sectors, general public, stakeholders and scientists. Although most of the researchers in astronomy (the main part of the potential users) consider the project still too risky and maybe not feasible in the short term to get some of the goals, there is a considerable percentage of astronomers that are highly interested and trust that an astronomical infrastructure based on balloons is possible and worth pursuing. It is estimated that we could impact around 800 researchers, 20 companies and around 2 million of persons with the dissemination, outreach and communication activities. The ORISON activities have been performed in 9 EU countries (see map in section 6), although the press releases had only an important impact in Spain.

4 POST-PROJECT ACTIVITIES

Several activities will be performed by ORISON team members without extra cost for the project in the next few months after formal completion of the project. Some of them are already listed, such as the future launch of a probe, but other are only drafted. Some of them are:

- Perseids press release.

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- Launch of SKYEYE probe.
 - Conclusion Workshop.
 - Newsletter.
 - European Planetary Science Congress 2017.
 - Other conferences.

5 ANNEX: PUBLIC PART OF THE ORISON POLL.

What is your main research topic?

14 respuestas

Please provide a short description of your research field

14 respuestas

test

Meteors

Galaxy formation and evolution; Cosmology

biology of stress

Stars, brown dwarfs, exoplanets

Planetary Sciences: solar system small bodies. But I am also interested in cosmic rays flux and its connection with solar activity and geomagnetic field.

very low-mass stars and exoplanets

Light Pollution monitoring

We do research on atmospheric electricity. In particular, models and observations (imaging and spectroscopy) of transient luminous events (TLE) in the upper atmosphere and lightning in the troposphere.

Cloud cover fracción and others astroclimatic parameters

Planetary Atmospheres

Observations of the High-z Universe

Exoplanetas

Quantum Communications aims at transferring and controlling quantum systems over large distances

What is your window of observation?

13 respuestas

Observing modes

13 respuestas

Tracking stability better than

10 respuestas

Your position

12 respuestas

Do you want that your scientific case be treated in a confidential way?

13 respuestas

Would your team or your institution be able to provide funds to at least cofund a small part of the infrastructure?

13 respuestas

Would your team or your institution prefer to procure observation time/data relevant to your science case rather than cofunding the infrastructure?

10 respuestas

Are you interested in a relatively simple infrastructure that can deploy instruments of around 8-30 kg? (Short development) (1-2 years)

13 respuestas

Are you interested in a more complex infrastructure that can deploy instruments of 30-100 kg? (Long development) (3-4 years)

13 respuestas

Are you interested in a really complex infrastructure that can deploy payloads of the order of 1000 kg or more? (Very long development) (>5 years). This is actually beyond the scope of ORISON but your feedback on this is also important

13 respuestas

What is the weight that you estimate for an instrument that would suit your needs?

10 respuestas

Would you prefer a permanent launching site or would you prefer mobility?

11 respuestas

Número de respuestas diarias

6 MAP OF ORISON EVENTS

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